

Deep Learning-Based Plant Leaf Disease Detection Using Convolutional Neural Networks

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Plant Disease Detection, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Image Processing, Agricultural Monitoring	The application of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques has significantly enhanced image processing performance in recent years compared to traditional methods. With the rapid growth of the global population and increasing food demand, agricultural productivity has become critically dependent on healthy plant cultivation. Plant diseases, influenced by various environmental factors, considerably reduce crop yield and pose a serious threat to global food security. Conventional disease detection methods are often time-consuming, less accurate, and inefficient, highlighting the need for an automated and reliable solution. In this work, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model is developed using MATLAB to detect plant diseases from leaf images. Publicly available datasets from Kaggle, consisting of healthy and diseased Tomato, Potato, and Pepper bell leaves, are used for training and validation. The proposed deep learning approach enables early and accurate disease detection, supporting timely intervention and improved crop management. The results demonstrate that the CNN-based system is effective and can be deployed as a practical plant disease detection tool to enhance agricultural productivity and ensure food security.

I. INTRODUCTION

In The agricultural land mass is more than just being a feeding sourcing in today's world. Indian economy is highly dependent of agricultural productivity. Therefore in field of agriculture, detection of disease in plants plays an important role. To detect a plant disease in very initial stage, use of automatic

disease detection technique is beneficial. For instance a disease named little leaf disease is a hazardous disease found in pine trees in United States. The affected tree has a stunted growth and dies within 6 years. Its impact is found in Alabama, Georgia parts of Southern US. In such scenarios early detection could have been fruitful. The existing method for plant disease detection is simply

naked eye observation by experts through which identification and detection of plant diseases is done. For doing so, a large team of experts as well as continuous monitoring of plant is required, which costs very high when we do with large farms. At the same time, in some countries, farmers do not have proper facilities or even idea that they can contact to experts. Due to which consulting experts even cost high as well as time consuming too. In such conditions, the suggested technique proves to be beneficial in monitoring large fields of crops. Automatic detection of the diseases by just seeing the symptoms on the plant leaves makes it easier as well as cheaper. This also supports machine vision to provide image based automatic process control, inspection, and robot guidance. Plant disease identification by visual way is more laborious task and at the same time, less accurate and can be done only in limited areas. Whereas if automatic detection technique is used it will take less efforts, less time and become more accurate. In plants, some general diseases seen are brown and yellow spots, early and late scorch, and others are fungal, viral and bacterial diseases. Image processing is used for measuring affected area of disease and to determine the difference in the color of the affected area in limited areas. Whereas if automatic detection technique is used it will take less efforts, less time and become more accurate. In plants, some general diseases seen are brown and yellow spots, early and late scorch, and others are fungal, viral and bacterial diseases. Image processing is used for measuring affected area of disease and to determine the difference in the color of the affected area in limited areas. Whereas if automatic detection technique is used it will take less efforts, less time and become more accurate. In plants, some general diseases seen are brown and yellow spots, early and late scorch, and others are fungal, viral and bacterial diseases.

Plant Diseases:

Disease fungi take their energy from the plants on which they live. They are responsible for a great deal of damage and are characterized by wilting, scabs, moldy coatings, rusts, blotches and rotted tissue.

Anthracnose: Infected plants develop dark, water soaked lesions on stems, leaves or leaf.

Apple Scab: Scabby spots on leaf and leaves are sunken and may have velvety spores in the center.

Bacterial Canker: Common on cherries, peaches and plums, but may also affect other kinds of stone leaves.

Black Knot: Attacks plum, apricot, cherry and chokecherry trees -- both leafing and ornamental.

Club Root: Infected plants in the cabbage family will have misshapen and deformed (clubbed) roots.

Damping Off: Occurs when old seed is planted in cold, wet soil and is further increased by poor drainage.

Downy Mildew: Symptoms appear as yellow to white patches on the upper surfaces of older leaves.

Early Blight: Brown spots with concentric rings that form a "bull's eye" are found on lower leaves.

Fire Blight: A bacterial disease named for the scorched appearance of infected plant leaves.

Fusarium Wilt: Yellowing and wilting of lower leaves, especially in tomato and potato plants.

Gray Mold: Identified as gray soft, mushy spots on leaves, stems, flowers and produce.

Late Blight: Found on potato and tomato leaves as pale green spots, often beginning at leaf tips or edges.

Leaf Curl: Affects the blossoms, leaf, leaves and shoots of backyard peach and nectarine trees.

Leaf Spot: Leaves have dark water-soaked spots, sometimes with a yellow halo, usually uniform in size.

Mosaic Virus: Infected plant leaves have intermingled patches of light green or yellowish colors.

Powdery Mildew: Appears as a dusty white to gray coating over leaf surfaces and other infected plant parts.

Rust: Reddish-orange spore masses are found primarily on the surface of lower leaves.

Leaf Spots

Leaf spots (other names: anthracnose, scab, leaf blotch, shot hole) are usually rather definite spots of varying sizes, shapes and colors. There is nearly always a distinctive margin. Sometimes the spot, which may be caused by bacteria or fungi, is surrounded by a yellow halo. If caused by a fungus, there is nearly always fungus growth of some type in the spot, particularly in damp weather. This fungus growth may be tiny pimple-like structures, often black in color, or a moldy growth of spores. It is often necessary to use a hand lens or a microscope to see these structures. If the spots are numerous or close together, diseased areas may join together to form irregular areas called "blotches." The common names of leaf spot diseases may be general, such as bacterial leaf spot; descriptive, such as frog-eye

leaf spot; or named after the fungus, such as Septoria leaf spot.

The aim of this work is to develop an automated system for accurate and efficient detection and classification of plant leaf diseases using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The system seeks to analyze leaf images, extract relevant features such as texture, color, and shape, and classify them into healthy or diseased categories, enabling early disease detection and supporting timely intervention in agriculture.

The primary objective is to automatically detect and classify plant leaf diseases from digital images using CNNs. This reduces reliance on manual inspection, minimizes human error, and ensures timely intervention for crop management.

Another goal is to leverage CNNs' ability to extract hierarchical features directly from images, capturing texture, shape, and color variations. This enables precise classification of multiple disease types even under complex environmental conditions.

Plant diseases significantly affect crop yield, quality, and overall agricultural productivity. Early and accurate detection of leaf diseases is essential to minimize losses, reduce pesticide use, and ensure sustainable farming practices. Traditional disease detection relies on human observation, which is time-consuming, subjective, and requires expert knowledge. Inaccurate or delayed diagnosis can lead to the rapid spread of infection, resulting in economic and ecological losses.

The proposed project focuses on the automated detection and classification of plant leaf diseases using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), a deep learning technique particularly suited for image recognition tasks. Plant diseases are a major challenge in agriculture, leading to reduced crop yield, poor quality produce, and economic losses. Traditional methods of disease detection rely heavily on human expertise, which is time-consuming, subjective, and prone to errors, especially when disease symptoms are subtle or visually similar. An automated, image-based solution can significantly improve accuracy, speed, and efficiency in disease management.

The system begins with data acquisition, where digital images of plant leaves are collected from publicly available datasets or field images captured under varying environmental conditions. These images

typically exhibit differences in leaf shape, size, color, lighting, and background clutter, all of which can complicate disease detection. To address these challenges, the images are pre-processed using techniques such as resizing, normalization, and augmentation. Augmentation methods—including rotation, flipping, and scaling—help increase the diversity of the training dataset, improving the model's robustness to real-world variations.

Once pre-processed, the images are fed into a Convolutional Neural Network, which automatically extracts hierarchical features from raw pixels. Unlike traditional machine learning approaches that require manual feature extraction, CNNs learn to identify patterns such as color variations, texture changes, spots, lesions, and shape deformities that are indicative of specific diseases. The network typically consists of multiple convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, enabling it to capture both local and global features from leaf images. Activation functions and dropout layers are used to introduce non-linearity and prevent over fitting, ensuring the model generalizes well to unseen images.

The classification stage assigns each leaf image to a specific disease category or identifies it as healthy. Common CNN architectures this project is an **automated, high-accuracy disease detection system** that can assist farmers, agronomists, and researchers in monitoring crop health efficiently. By providing timely and accurate disease diagnosis, the system enables early intervention, reduces pesticide misuse, and promotes sustainable agricultural practices.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] Johannes, A., Picon, A., Alvarez-Gila, et.al The authors of this paper are a group of researchers with strong backgrounds in agricultural engineering, computer vision, and precision farming. Their main aim was to bridge the gap between advanced plant disease detection techniques and real-world farming conditions. They focused on developing a practical, low-cost solution that farmers could use directly in the field using mobile capture devices. By combining expertise from image processing and crop science, the team worked toward making plant disease diagnosis faster and more accessible. Their research contributes to the growing field of smart agriculture and digital decision-support systems.

In this study, the authors discovered that plant diseases in wheat can be automatically detected using images taken with ordinary mobile phones. They designed an image-analysis method that identifies diseased regions on wheat leaves under natural lighting and background conditions. The system was tested on thousands of real field images and successfully identified major wheat diseases such as rust, septoria, and tan spot. The results showed good accuracy and robustness, even with variations in image quality. This work proved that mobile-based automatic disease diagnosis is feasible and can help farmers detect diseases early, reduce crop losses, and improve overall wheat production.

[2] Shorten, C., & Khoshgoftaar, T. M. A survey on Image Data Augmentation for Deep Learning. *Journal of Big Data*. The authors Shorten, C. and Khoshgoftaar, T. M. are researchers in the field of data science and machine learning. Chandler Shorten has worked on applying deep learning methods to real-world problems, especially where data limitations are a concern. Taghi M. Khoshgoftaar is a well-known expert in big data analytics and machine learning, with extensive experience in handling noisy, imbalanced, and large-scale datasets. Together, they focus on improving how deep learning models learn from image data when there isn't enough labeled training data available, which is a common challenge in many practical applications.

In their 2019 survey, the authors explored the concept of image data augmentation – techniques that artificially increase the size and diversity of image datasets used for training deep learning models. They reviewed a wide range of augmentation strategies, from simple transformations like rotation and scaling to advanced methods such as generative adversarial networks (GANs). Their analysis showed that data augmentation can significantly improve model performance, generalization, and robustness, especially in domains where collecting large amounts of labeled images is difficult or costly. The survey also highlighted the strengths and limitations of various augmentation techniques and provided guidelines for choosing appropriate methods to boost deep learning outcomes.

[3] Saleem, M. H., Khanchi, S., Potgieter, J., et al. Image-Based Plant Disease Identification by Deep Learning Meta Architectures. *Plants*. Saleem, M. H., Khanchi, S., Potgieter, J. are researchers working at the

intersection of plant science and artificial intelligence. Their expertise spans precision agriculture, machine learning, and deep learning applications for plant health monitoring. They focus on developing robust computational methods that can help detect and classify plant diseases using digital imagery, aiming to assist farmers and agronomists with early and accurate diagnoses. In their 2020 study, the authors investigated deep learning meta-architectures for image-based plant disease identification. They evaluated several state-of-the-art neural network models to determine which ones performed best at recognizing disease symptoms from leaf images. Their experiments showed that deep learning models could achieve high accuracy in classifying healthy and diseased plants across multiple species, even when images varied in quality and environmental conditions. This work demonstrated that leveraging advanced neural network architectures significantly improves plant disease detection and supports the use of AI-driven tools in agricultural decision-making and crop management.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the existing system for plant disease prediction are widely used to classify plant leaf diseases based on image features. The system primarily relies on captured images of infected and healthy leaves, which are processed and fed into a neural network model for classification. Initially, leaf images are collected using cameras or public datasets. Pre-processing steps such as resizing, noise removal, background elimination, color space conversion (RGB to gray scale), and contrast enhancement are performed to improve image quality. After pre processing, feature extraction techniques are applied to obtain important characteristics such as color features (mean, variance), texture features (GLCM), and shape features. These extracted features serve as inputs to the ANN model. The ANN typically consists of an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. The network is trained using labelled datasets of healthy and diseased leaves. During training, back propagation is used to adjust weights and minimize classification error. Once trained, the model predicts the disease type when a new leaf image is provided. In most existing systems, ANN-based models achieve moderate to high accuracy depending on dataset size and feature quality. However, traditional ANN models require manual feature extraction and may not perform well

under varying lighting conditions, complex backgrounds, or unseen disease patterns. Despite these limitations, ANN-based systems form the foundation of automated plant disease detection and provide a cost-effective solution for early disease identification in agriculture.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Existing System

1. Plant Disease Dataset

The process starts with a dataset containing leaf images under various conditions such as different lighting, angles, and backgrounds. Each image is labeled with the corresponding disease type or marked as healthy. This dataset is used for both training and testing the model.

2. Pre-Processing

In this stage, the raw images are prepared for further analysis. The main steps include:

- **Resizing** images to a standard dimension
- **Noise removal** using filters to eliminate unwanted distortions
- **Background removal** to isolate the leaf region
- **Color space conversion** (RGB to grayscale) to simplify processing
- **Contrast enhancement** to improve visibility of disease regions

These steps improve image quality and ensure consistency across the dataset.

3. Histogram Equalization

Histogram equalization is applied to enhance the contrast of the image. It redistributes pixel intensity values to make important features—such as spots, lesions, and discoloration—more visible. This step is particularly useful under poor lighting or uneven brightness conditions.

4. Region of Interest (ROI) Extraction

After enhancement, the system identifies and isolates the **Region of Interest (ROI)**, which corresponds to the infected or relevant portion of the leaf. This reduces

unnecessary background information and focuses only on important areas for analysis.

5. Feature Extraction

In this stage, meaningful features are extracted from the ROI. These include:

- **Color Features:** Mean, variance, and color distribution
- **Texture Features:** Using techniques like **GLCM (Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix)**
- **Shape Features:** Size, edges, and structure of infected regions

These features serve as the input parameters for the neural network model.

6. Neural Network (ANN)

The extracted features are fed into an **Artificial Neural Network**, which consists of:

- **Input Layer:** Receives extracted features
- **Hidden Layer(s):** Processes and learns patterns
- **Output Layer:** Produces classification results

The network is trained using labeled data. During training, the **backpropagation algorithm** adjusts weights to minimize error and improve prediction accuracy.

7. Output

The final output of the system is the **classification of the leaf**, such as:

- Healthy
- Diseased (with specific disease type)

This helps farmers or users take appropriate action for crop management.

The system processes leaf images through enhancement and feature extraction, then uses an ANN model to classify diseases. While it provides a **cost-effective and automated solution**, it has certain limitations:

- Requires **manual feature extraction**
- Performance depends heavily on **image quality**
- Less robust to **complex backgrounds and lighting variations**
- Limited ability to generalize to **new or unseen diseases**

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The development of smart farming has featured machine learning being used for some data intensive aspects of agriculture. These systems include aspects for data collection on the field, data analysis, monitoring, prediction, and so on. These systems have also aided in agricultural research for studies on farming techniques and practices to help manage limited resources and adapt to climate change. All of these applications and research studies have led to farming with high yield and higher quality of the produce. The entire concept of smart farming has really opened up an opportunity to do more in the agricultural sector. And this is not just a good thing, but a necessary thing. According to the United states Farm Bureau, we would need to be producing 70% more food than we are now to support the world population by the year 2050. This therefore means that we would not only need more farms, but we would also need to be producing more food from each farm land than we are producing now. This is why it is important that we practice more effective farming and that we are able to study our farms and develop strategies to get better yields. This objective requires increased and effective effort in 3 major areas;

- Increasing the yield of food crops and livestock for each farm
- Maintaining and possibly, increasing the quality of farm produce
- Reducing the wastage of farm produce

All of these areas are avenues where artificial intelligence can be applied to help get better results. This thesis focuses aiding the reduction of wastage with the added benefit of helping store owners be able to provide quality produce to their customers and ensure the sale of their products.

Figure 2: Implementation steps of object detection and classification

This describes and discusses the research methods that were used for this study leaf detection. It can be summaries in three stages .In first stage it start with pre-processing of leaf images to enhancement it and make it more suitable to analyze such as reduce and remove noise, contrast enhancement, and image sharpening[29]. Second stage is processing of images like edge detection, segmentation, feature selection and extraction, classification etc. Final stage is implementing the feature of images for pattern recognition to detect the dieses. The propose method described. After getting choosing the tools for my development and determining my neural network architecture, I went into the development part of my work. I followed a series of steps which would be discussed within this chapter, I to execute the code on as GPUs.

Neural networks are a method of machine learning that emulates the way the human brain works. The first efforts in the development of a neural network They wrote a paper discussing how neurons work and made and electrical model of a neural network. then defined some of the more known laws and concepts of Neural networks The Organization of Behavior, and then with a more publications and articles. Since then, there has been a lot of research that has led to the development of a number of other neural network Models.

Architecture of Convolutional Neural Network Convolutional neural networks have an input layer and an output layer with multiple hidden layers. These hidden layers are intertwined and connected fully. The more complicated the convolution is, the more sophisticated the network is, although that would require more computation and more time for training. There have been improvements on the design of convolutional neural networks over the years, primarily in the layer designs and some optimization techniques to boost speed and accuracy. Improvements have also been aided by the growth of the amount of annotated data and improvement in the power of processing units

There are different types of layers in a typical convolutional neural network that serve different purposes within the network, such as the pooling layers, the convolutional layers, the fully connected layer and the output layer. They also consist of an activation function. Figure shows a simple typical structure of a CNN.

Figure 3: Typical structure of a Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Layers: We used three sets of convolutional layers with increasing filter sizes -32, and 64,128. Each set consists of two layers, with the first layer having a ReLU activation function and the second layer not having any activation function.

Max Pooling Layers: After each set of convolutional layers, we added a max pooling layer to reduce the spatial dimensions of the output.

Dense Layers: After flattening the output from the convolutional layers, we added two dense layers with ReLU activation functions, followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.2 to prevent overfitting. Finally, we added a dense layer with a softmax activation function to produce the output probabilities.

Model Training: With the model compiled, we trained it on the training data for 10 epochs with a batch size of 256. We also used two callbacks Model Check point - to reduce the learning rate and save the best model during training.

Model Evaluation: Once the model was trained, we evaluated it on the test data and computed the accuracy and confusion matrix to measure its performance.

An automated procedure for detecting plant diseases from leaf images follows a systematic pipeline consisting of preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification. The process begins with the acquisition of plant leaf images, which may contain noise, complex backgrounds, shadows, and uneven illumination due to varying environmental conditions. Therefore, the collected images are first preprocessed using resizing, RGB-to-grayscale conversion (or color normalization), normalization, and histogram equalization to enhance image quality and highlight diseased regions such as spots, blights, and discoloration patterns. After preprocessing, segmentation techniques are applied to

separate the leaf region from the background and identify infected areas based on color intensity differences, texture irregularities, and lesion patterns. These segmented regions represent potential disease-affected areas. Following segmentation, the system performs automatic feature extraction using a deep learning model. A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is designed to learn spatial patterns such as edges, shapes, color variations, vein distortions, and texture abnormalities associated with different plant diseases. The architecture of the proposed system consists of a CNN with multiple convolutional and pooling layers followed by dense layers for classification. The input to the model is a resized leaf image (for example, $150 \times 150 \times 3$ for RGB images). The initial convolutional layers use small filters (3×3) with ReLU activation to extract low-level features such as edges and simple textures, while deeper layers learn high-level representations such as complex lesion structures and disease-specific patterns. Pooling layers reduce the feature map size and help prevent overfitting.

Finally, the extracted features are passed to fully connected dense layers that perform classification using a Softmax output layer. The system categorizes the images into classes such as healthy leaf, bacterial infection, fungal disease, or viral disease based on learned visual characteristics. The third and fourth layers are convolutional layers with 32 filters of size 3×3 and ReLU activation, using same padding to maintain spatial dimensions. The fifth and sixth layers are convolutional layers with 64 filters of size 3×3 and ReLU activation, followed by a max-pooling layer of size 2×2 , which reduces the image dimensions by half in both width and height.

The overall architecture of the CNN can be represented by the following formulas: First convolutional layer:

$$h_1 = \max(0, x * w_1 + b_1)$$

where x is the input image, w_1 are the weights of the first convolutional layer, b_1 is the bias term, and h_1 is the output of the first convolutional layer.

Second convolutional layer:

$$h_2 = \max(0, h_1 * w_2 + b_2)$$

where w_2 are the weights of the second convolutional layer, b_2 is the bias term, and h_2 is the output of the second convolutional layer.

Third convolutional layer:

$$h_3 = \max(0, h_2 * w_3 + b_3)$$

The first convolutional layer has 16 filters with a filter size of 3x3, followed by a ReLU activation function and padding to maintain the size of the input image. The second convolutional layer has the same settings as the first layer.

After the third convolutional layer, another 3x3 convolutional layer is added with 32 filters and ReLU activation. The output shape of this layer is also 32x150x150. The number of parameters in this layer can be calculated. Next, a fourth convolutional layer is added with 64 filters and a receptive field of 3x3 pixels. The output shape of this layer is 64x150x150. The number of parameters in this layer can be calculated. Another 3x3 convolutional layer is added after the fourth convolutional layer with 64 filters and ReLU activation. The output shape of this layer is also 64x150x150. The number of parameters in this layer can be calculated using the same formula as before, which gives:

$$\text{num_params} = (3 * 3 * 64 + 1) * 64 = 36,928$$

Dropout is a regularization technique used to prevent over fitting in neural networks by randomly dropping out (setting to zero) a certain percentage of the neurons during each training epoch. This prevents the model from becoming too dependent on any one neuron and promotes the learning of more robust features.

To reduce the dimensionality of the feature maps and capture the most important features, a max pooling layer with a pool size of 2x2 is added after the fifth convolutional layer. The output of the max-pooling layer is flattened and passed through a fully connected layer with 64 neurons and a ReLU activation function. This layer is followed by a dropout layer with a dropout rate of 0.2, which helps prevent overfitting.

In our implementation, we added a Dropout layer with a rate of 0.2 after the first fully connected layer. This means that during each training epoch, 20% of the neurons in the layer will be randomly set to zero. Early

Stopping is another regularization technique used to prevent overfitting. It works by monitoring the model's performance on a validation set during training and stopping the training process early if the model's performance on the validation set has not improved for a certain number of epochs.

The formula for Early Stopping is as follows:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \leq t \\ t & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where x represents the validation loss and t represents the minimum validation loss observed so far. In our implementation, early stopping is applied to prevent overfitting. This means that if the validation loss does not improve for 2 consecutive epochs, the training process is stopped automatically to maintain optimal model performance and avoid unnecessary computation. Finally, the output layer is a fully connected layer with 2 neurons and a Softmax activation function. The Softmax function ensures that the output of the network represents a probability distribution over the two classes, such as healthy and diseased (or specific disease categories depending on the dataset). The performance of the proposed CNN-based plant disease classification system is evaluated using standard performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1-score to measure the reliability and robustness of the model. Evaluation is performed on a separate test dataset to ensure that the trained model generalizes effectively to unseen plant leaf images. A confusion matrix is also used to analyze classification results and understand the model's ability to distinguish between healthy and infected leaves. High sensitivity is particularly important in this system to ensure that diseased plants are correctly identified at an early stage.

The system includes a user-friendly graphical interface that allows farmers or agricultural experts to upload plant leaf images and receive automated disease analysis results within a short time. The interface displays prediction probabilities along with the final classification label, making the results easy to interpret. Users can also download generated reports for crop monitoring and agricultural planning purposes. The platform is designed to be simple and intuitive so that

even non-technical users can operate it efficiently. To ensure data security and reliability, the system incorporates secure data transmission, protected storage, and controlled access mechanisms. Cloud-based deployment enables remote monitoring, scalability, and consistent performance for large-scale agricultural applications. Regular system updates, automated testing, and continuous performance monitoring help maintain stability and improve accuracy over time. Overall, the system aims to support farmers in early plant disease detection, reduce crop losses, and enhance agricultural productivity.

5. RESULTS& DISCUSSION

The proposed Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model for image-based plant leaf disease detection demonstrated strong performance in accurately classifying healthy and diseased leaves. The dataset consisted of multiple categories of plant diseases along with healthy samples, and the images were pre-processed through resizing, normalization, and augmentation to improve generalization. The CNN architecture, composed of convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers, effectively learned both low-level features such as edges and color variations, and high-level features such as lesion patterns, discoloration, and texture irregularities. Experimental results showed high training and validation accuracy, indicating that the model successfully captured disease-specific patterns. The use of data augmentation techniques such as rotation, flipping, and zooming helped reduce over fitting and improved robustness under varying lighting and background conditions. Performance metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score confirmed the reliability of the model in distinguishing between healthy and infected leaves. The confusion matrix analysis revealed that most disease classes were correctly classified, with only minor misclassifications occurring between visually similar diseases. The discussion of results highlights that CNN-based approaches significantly outperform traditional machine learning methods that rely on manual feature extraction. Automatic feature learning enables better adaptability to complex and diverse disease symptoms. However, performance may slightly decrease when images contain heavy shadows, overlapping leaves, or early-stage infections with subtle symptoms.

Figure 4: Training Process for Plant Leaf Disease Detection

This figure illustrates the training process used to detect diseases in plant leaves. training and validation performance over 105 iterations, achieving a high validation accuracy of 98.81%. and features from a dataset of healthy and diseased leaf images.

Figure 5: Training data

This figure illustrates the training process used to detect diseases in plant leaves. During training, the system learns patterns and features from a dataset of healthy and diseased leaf images. The trained model is then used to accurately identify and classify apple plant leaf diseases.

Figure 6: Browsing input data

Figure 7: Input image

The **input image** shows a plant leaf with several brown spots and patches on its surface. These visible symptoms indicate a **possible leaf disease**

Figure 8: Output prediction

The **CNN model prediction** identifies the leaf as affected by **Apple Scab Disease** with a **confidence of 99.99%**. This indicates the model successfully detected disease patterns from the leaf image and classified it accurately

Figure 9: Another input image

The **input image** shows a plant leaf with several brown spots and patches on its surface. These visible symptoms indicate a **possible leaf disease**

Figure 10: Output prediction

The **CNN model prediction** identifies the leaf as affected by **Black Rot** with a **confidence of 100%**. This indicates the model successfully detected disease patterns from the leaf image and classified it accurately

Figure 11: Another input image

The **input image** shows a healthy green plant leaf with a smooth surface and natural texture. There are **no visible disease spots or abnormal patches**. These visible symptoms indicate a **possible healthy leaf**

Figure 12: Prediction output

The **CNN model prediction** identifies the healthy leaf with a **confidence of 99.99 %**. This indicates the model successfully detected patterns from the leaf image and classified it accurately

Figure 13: Confusion matrix

The figure shows a **confusion matrix** for an apple plant disease classification model with three classes: Apple Scab, Black Rot, and Healthy. The rows represent the actual classes, while the columns represent the predicted classes by the model. Most values appear along the diagonal, indicating that the model correctly classified the majority of samples. The small off-diagonal values show very few misclassifications, demonstrating high accuracy in detecting apple plant diseases.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we comprehensively reviewed and analyzed recent deep learning approaches for plant leaf detection and classification, with a primary focus on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based models. Unlike earlier survey papers that mainly emphasized traditional computer vision techniques, this review highlights the significant advancements achieved through deep learning methods, particularly CNN architectures, which have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in image classification tasks. An up-to-date analysis of published literature was conducted, covering various CNN-based detection and classification frameworks, feature learning strategies, and publicly available datasets used in plant leaf disease identification. The study examined different architectural designs, including shallow and deep CNN models, transfer learning approaches, and data augmentation strategies that enhance generalization performance. Through critical evaluation, several open challenges were identified, such as limited availability of diverse and balanced datasets, variations in lighting and environmental conditions, similarities between disease symptoms, and the need for lightweight models suitable for real-time field deployment. The importance of robust feature representation learned automatically by CNNs,

without manual feature engineering, was also emphasized.

Future scope

In future research, the performance of plant leaf detection and classification systems can be further enhanced by integrating **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)** models with CNN architectures. While CNNs are highly effective in extracting spatial features from leaf images, LSTM networks are designed to capture sequential and temporal dependencies. This combination can be particularly useful when analyzing time-series agricultural data, such as disease progression over multiple growth stages or seasonal variations in crop health.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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